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LIVESTOCK DEVELOPMENT PROBLEMS AND PROSPECTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: Livestock production contributes to a total gross output of agriculture in Uzbekistan, amounting to 426,264.0 billion soums. The significance of this sector lies in its contribution to the income generation of rural inhabitants, thus positioning the issues and potential growth opportunities at the forefront of agricultural policy in Uzbekistan. The area of pastures managed by agricultural producers sharply decreased. Individual farmers and dekhkans feel the lack of fodder for complete nutrition and production of dairy products. One of the factors hindering the development of dairy farming is the small size of the main part of producers in this sector. Milk is mainly produced on private household plots and for personal consumption. Small producers do not have the opportunity to introduce advanced standards of zootechnics, effectively sell their products, as well as to purchase good fodder crops.

State assistance in the realm of animal husbandry primarily manifests in the form of advantageous loans extended to livestock product producers and fiscal advantages granted to processors of such commodities. All over the country there are veterinary stations which provide vaccination, treatment and artificial insemination of cattle to farms and dekhkan farms. At the same time, these procedures are often related to the need to incur additional costs for these activities. Artificial insemination uses a small number of agricultural producers. This report reveals the current state, problems and prospects of dairy farming development in Uzbekistan. Recommendations on improvement of the state policy in this sphere are given.

Key words: veterinary service, food safety, volume of products, animal husbandry, dairy farming, agriculture, agricultural sector, Uzbekistan, dekhkan farms, livestock industry, market economy, productive feed crops.

Annotatsiya: O'zbekiston qishloq xo'jaligining umumiy yalpi mahsulotida chorvachilik mahsulotlari 426264,0 mlrd.so'mni tashkil etadi. Ushbu sektorning ahamiyati uning qishloq aholisining daromadlarini oshirishga qo'shgan hissasi bilan bog'liq bo'lib, shu tariqa O'zbekiston qishloq xo'jaligi siyosatida muammolar va rivojlanish imkoniyatlarini birinchi o'ringa qo'yadi. Qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqaruvchilari tasarrufidagi yaylovlar maydoni keskin qisqardi. Ayrim fermer va dehqonlar to'liq oziqlantirish va sut mahsulotlari yetishtirish uchun yem-xashak yetishmasligini his qilmoqda. Sut chorvachiligining rivojlanishiga to'sqinlik qilayotgan omillardan biri bu tarmoqdagi ishlab chiqaruvchilarning asosiy qismining kichikligidir. Sut asosan shaxsiy tomorqalarda va shaxsiy iste'mol uchun ishlab chiqariladi. Kichik ishlab chiqaruvchilar zootexnikaning ilg'or standartlarini joriy etish, o'z mahsulotlarini samarali sotish, shuningdek, yaxshi yem-xashak ekinlarini xarid qilish imkoniyatiga ega emas.

Chorvachilik sohasidagi davlat yordami, birinchi navbatda, chorvachilik mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqaruvchilarga beriladigan imtiyozli kreditlar va bunday mahsulotlarni qayta ishlovchilarga beriladigan fiskal imtiyozlar ko'rinishida namoyon bo'ladi. Respublikamiz bo'ylab fermer va dehqon xo'jaliklarini emlash, davolash va qoramollarni sun'iy urug'lantirish bilan shug'ullanuvchi veterinariya punktlari faoliyat ko'rsatmoqda. Shu bilan birga, ushbu tartib-qoidalar ko'pincha ushbu faoliyat uchun qo'shimcha xarajatlarni talab qilish zarurati bilan bog'liq. Sun'iy urug'lantirishda kichik miqdordagi qishloq xo'jaligi ishlab chiqaruvchilari qo'llaniladi. Ushbu ma'ruza O'zbekistonda sut chorvachiligini rivojlantirishning bugungi holati, muammolari va istiqbollari ochib beradi. Bu boradagi davlat siyosatini takomillashtirish yuzasidan tavsiyalar berildi.

Kalit so'zlar: veterinariya xizmati, oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, mahsulot hajmi, chorvachilik, sut chorvachiligi, qishloq xo'jaligi, qishloq xo'jaligi, O'zbekiston, dehqon xo'jaliklari, chorvachilik sanoati, bozor iqtisodiyoti, mahsuldor yem ekinlari.

Аннотация: Продукция животноводства вносит вклад в общий валовой выпуск сельского хозяйства Узбекистана, составляющий 426,264,0 млрд.сум. Значение этого сектора заключается в его вкладе в создание доходов сельских жителей, что ставит проблемы и потенциальные возможности роста на передний план сельскохозяйственной политики в Узбекистане. Резко сократилась площадь пастбищ, находящихся в ведении сельхозпроизводителей. Отдельные фермеры и дехкане ощущают нехватку кормов для полноценного питания и производства молочной продукции. Одним из факторов, сдерживающих развитие молочного животноводства, является небольшой размер основной части производителей этого сектора. Молоко в основном производится в личных подсобных хозяйствах и для личного потребления. Мелкие производители не имеют возможности внедрять передовые стандарты зоотехники, эффективно реализовывать свою продукцию, а также приобретать хорошие кормовые культуры.

Государственная помощь в сфере животноводства проявляется, прежде всего, в форме льготных кредитов, предоставляемых производителям продукции животноводства, и налоговых льгот, предоставляемых переработчикам такой продукции. По всей стране действуют ветеринарные станции, обеспечивающие вакцинацию, лечение и искусственное осеменение крупного рогатого скота в фермерских и дехканских хозяйствах. В то же время данные процедуры зачастую связаны с необходимостью нести дополнительные расходы на данные мероприятия. Искусственное осеменение использует небольшое количество сельхозпроизводителей. В данном отчете раскрывается современное состояние, проблемы и перспективы развития молочного животноводства в Узбекистане. Даны рекомендации по совершенствованию государственной политики в этой сфере.

Ключевые слова: ветеринарная служба, безопасность пищевых продуктов, объем продукции, животноводство, молочное животноводство, сельское хозяйство, аграрный сектор, Узбекистан, дехканские хозяйства, животноводство, рыночная экономика, продуктивные кормовые культуры.

INTRODUCTION

For centuries, the livestock industry has played an important role in the economic and social life of the people of Central Asia. During the transition period of the economy, production in many industries declined, and in difficult years, with the restriction of people's ability to have additional income, this area made a significant contribution to maintaining sustainable of the level of well-being of the population in rural areas. Animal husbandry has become an important source of food and income for the rural population. On this day, when the mechanisms of the market economy are activated, the demand for food is growing, the task of further increasing the efficiency and competitiveness of this industry plays an important role.

Large-scale work has been carried out in our country to ensure a sustainable increase in livestock and poultry, strengthen veterinary control and improve the quality of veterinary service, organize effective work to protect animal health, ensure epizootic calm and food safety.

At the same time, it is necessary to implement a set of state support measures to improve livestock breeding, strengthen the feed base, livestock breeding and increase the number of large business entities in the cultivation of livestock products ^[1].

In January-December 2023, the volume of agricultural, forestry and fisheries products amounted to 426,264,0 billion sums or 104.1% to the corresponding period of 2022, including services in agriculture and animal husbandry, hunting and in these areas – 411,594,6 billion sums (104.1%), forestry – 10,399,5 billion sums (102.7%), fisheries – 4,269,9 billion sums (107.4%).

Agriculture, forestry and fisheries are associated with an increase in the volume of products (services), mainly with an increase in the volume of agricultural production (4.1%). The growth of agricultural products in all categories of farms is 7.3%, silk raw materials – 6.5%, raw cotton – 6.0%, grain – 5.5%, melons – 5.5%, fruits and berries – 4.1%, eggs – 4.4%, meat – 3.9%, potatoes – 3.8%.

Analysis by economic categories shows that 63.1% of the total volume of agricultural products are dekhkan and household farms, 29.8% are farms, 7.1% are farms engaged in agricultural activities ^[2].

Animal husbandry is one of the dynamically developing sectors of agriculture in Uzbekistan, which accounts for 63.1 percent of agricultural products produced in the country, of which 29.8 percent are farms, 7.1 percent are agricultural organizations. The main feature of the industry is that the main part of livestock production is produced in not very large family (dekhkan) farms. The average size of the area occupied by these farms is 0.15 hectares. According to the Statistics Agency, in 2023, the total volume of agricultural, forestry and fisheries products (services) amounted to 426.3 trillion sums. The production of livestock products in dekhkan farms is of great social importance. Therefore, this is an important source of income and consumption for many families. However, the localization of most livestock farms leads to a limitation of the possibility of obtaining a positive effect through the application of modern technologies and "economies of scale." This is manifested at a low level of industry performance indicators.

There are other problems of livestock development in the country. One of the most serious problems is the shortage of feed, which is associated with an excessive reduction in the sowing areas of feed crops (since 1991, despite the increase in livestock by 45 percent, sowing areas have decreased by 70 percent). An urgent problem for agricultural producers is also the insufficient development of service infrastructure.

Due to soil salinization and water erosion associated with improper implementation of reclamation activities, large areas of irrigated land are annually removed from agricultural circulation.

Small-scale livestock farms have limited access to land and are making efforts to supply their animals with seasonal feed, especially during winter, when demand for animal food and market prices are at their highest levels. 43.2% of respondents would like to use more land for pasture land. But 93.7 per cent said they lacked land to rent. Grazing on public pastures, including by hired herders, is not very common due to a lack of grazing land. Public pastures mean unallocated land located mainly in desert areas.

The growth of livestock has led to a deterioration in the quality of pasture, primarily as a result of private and haphazard grazing, as well as non-compliance with pasture turnover.

Not only the quality of pastures is deteriorating, but also arable land, which reduces the ability to sow feed crops. Deterioration of land quality is associated with the following factors:

Cultivation of two main crops (cotton and winter grains), lack of crop rotation and intercropping, untimely and inadequate reclamation activities, as well as catastrophic drying of the Aral Sea. To date, more than half of irrigated land is affected by salinity to varying degrees. The soil appraisal score decreased accordingly and is less than 55 in the republic. The area of high quality irrigated land has declined by more than 80% since 1990, effectively meaning that it is currently completely absent. Good quality land areas also declined by 25%. Terms of access to financial resources and their sources.

There are a number of public and private banks that operate in the agriculture sector in the country, such as Hamkorbank, Xalk Bank, Agrobank, Qishlock Qurilish Bank and others. However, their high interest rates (18–24% per year) do not allow loans to most small livestock farms and are a serious burden on processing enterprises.

The main reason for not getting a loan is that the project was not profitable enough. This was stated by 6 dekhkan farms, 3 livestock and 4 mixfarm. Also, 5 dekhkan farms stated that they did not receive a loan because all funds in the bank were exhausted.

In general: The government should play an active role in providing land plots for the production of feed and lifting administrative restrictions related to land allocation. It is important to improve feed supply channels, ensure compliance with quality standards and monitoring feed quality, encourage scientific research for the development of highly productive feed crops, and provide training and vocational education for farmers and the entire rural population. In addition, the government should consider the issues of land tenure, the creation of a market for land rights and government control over the production.

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